

WHAT IS DIFERENCES HAVE AMIRICAN ENGLISH AND BRITISH ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article deals with significant data about role of English language in the modern world. On the other hand, in the article basic differences between American English and British English were analyzed.

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It is known that language is our primary way of communication as a species. Through it we are able to share our ideas, our needs and wants, and thoughts with others. There are more than 6,500 languages all over the world. Mostly we recognize them by the countries or geographic areas, languages are used in. Some are spoken by millions and some by only a few hundreds. The English language is spoken all over the world today. No matter where you travel to, you will surely find someone who speaks English. Although, there are other predominant languages by speakers such as Spanish or Mandarin, it is most probable to find an English speaker in Egypt than someone who speaks Spanish. That's why when you travel abroad, you will find flight instructions in English regardless of the airline you are traveling with. In addition, more than 500 million people use English on the internet, that gives an English speaker a tremendous advantage at the time of acquiring information from the net. There are some noticeable differences between British English and American English. One of the most noticeable differences is in pronunciation[1].

There are many reasons for these differences, including the influence of other languages, the different histories of the two countries, and even the different climate! But whatever the reason, it's important to be aware of these differences if you want to be understood when speaking English. The main difference between British English and American English is in pronunciation. Some words are also different in each variety of English, and there are also a few differences in the way they use grammar[2]. The British actually introduced the language to the Americas when they reached these lands by sea between the 16th and 17th centuries. At that time, spelling had not yet been standardised. It took the writing of the first dictionaries to set in stone how these words appeared. In the UK, the dictionary was compiled by London-based scholars. Meanwhile, in the United States, the lexicographer was a man named Noah Webster. Allegedly, he changed how the words were spelled to make the American version different from the British as a way of showing cultural independence from its mother country.

In terms of speech, the differences between American and British English actually took place after the first settlers arrived in America. These groups of people spoke using what was called rhotic speech, where the 'r' sounds of words are pronounced. Meanwhile, the higher classes in the UK wanted to distinguish the way they spoke from the common masses by softening their pronunciation of the 'r' sounds. Since the elite even back then were considered the standard for being fashionable, other people began to copy their speech, until it eventually became the common way of speaking in the south of England.

Spelling differences

British and American English have some spelling differences. The common ones are presented in the table below.

British English	American English
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-oe-/-ae- (e.g. anaemia, diarrhoea, encyclopaedia)	-e- (e.g. anemia, diarrhea, encyclopedia)
-t (e.g. burnt, dreamt, leapt)	-ed (e.g. burned, dreamed, leaped)
-ence (e.g. defence, offence, licence)	-ense (defense, offense, license)
-ell- (e.g. cancelled, jeweller, marvellous)	-el- (e.g. canceled, jeweler, marvelous)
-ise (e.g. appetiser, familiarise, organise)	-ize (e.g. appetizer, familiarize, organize)
-l- (e.g. enrol, fulfil, skilful)	-ll- (e.g. enroll, fulfill, skillfull)
-ogue (e.g. analogue, monologue, catalogue)	-og (e.g. analog, monolog, catalog) *Note that American English also recognizes words spelled with –ogue
-ou (e.g. colour, behaviour, mould)	-o (e.g. color, behavior, mold)
-re (e.g. metre, fibre, centre)	-er (e.g. meter, fiber, center)
-y- (e.g. tyre)	-i- (e.g. tire)

Vocabulary differences

The Americans and the British also have some words that differ from each

other. The table below lists some of the everyday objects that have different names, depending on what form of English you are using.

British English	American English
trousers	pants
flat	apartment
bonnet (the front of the car)	hood

Grammar differences

Aside from spelling and vocabulary, there are certain grammar differences between British and American English. For instance, in American English, collective nouns are considered singular (e.g. The band is playing). In contrast, collective nouns can be either singular or plural in British English, although the plural form is most often used (e.g. The band are playing).

- The British are also more likely to use formal speech, such as ‘shall’, whereas Americans favour the more informal ‘will’ or ‘should’.
- Americans, however, continue to use ‘gotten’ as the past participle of ‘get’, which the British have long since dropped in favour of ‘got’.
- ‘Needn’t’, which is commonly used in British English, is rarely, if at all used in American English. In its place is ‘don’t need to’.
- In British English, ‘at’ is the preposition in relation to time and place. However, in American English, ‘on’ is used instead of the former and ‘in’ for the latter.

While there may be certain differences between British and American English, the key takeaway is that the two have more similarities[3]. Accidentally using one instead of the other will not automatically lead to miscommunication. Americans

and Brits can usually communicate with each other without too much difficulty, so don't be too hard on yourself if you are unable to memorise the nuances of both languages.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that English has become a lingua franca or a common language of communication between people who do not share a common language[4]. It is often used in international meetings, conferences, and events where people from different countries come together. In such situations, English serves as a neutral language that can be understood by everyone. English as a lingua franca has facilitated global communication and has become an essential tool for international diplomacy. English has become the language of international business. In today's global economy, businesses need to communicate effectively with partners and clients from different parts of the world. English has become the common language of business communication, and proficiency in English is now a prerequisite for many jobs. English has also become the language of trade and commerce, making it essential for businesses to have a good command of the language to succeed in the global market. Learning differences between American and British English helps you utilize English effectively wherever.

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[The Role of English in the Globalized World – My Blog \(verbvalley.com\)](#)